

Figure Z16

Figure Z16: Within-tissue communication at cell-type level. Within-tissue ligand-receptor networks across the three tissues (row panels) in the four intervention groups (column panels). Number of interactions (heatmaps) between source cell types with ligand (rows) and target cell types with interacting receptors (columns) are plotted. Cell-type pairs with relatively higher number of interactions in each heatmap are highlighted using red rectangles. A list of abbreviations used in this figure appear in the Methods.